

AN APPROXIMATE ANALYTIC SOLUTION FOR THE STRESSES AND DISPLACEMENTS OF THIN-WALLED COMPOSITE BEAMS WITH MONO-SYMMETRIC CROSS-SECTIONS SUBJECTED TO BENDING

Marko Vukasović¹, Radoslav Pavazza¹

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering and Naval Architecture, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering and Naval Architecture, University of Split
Rudjera Boskovicica 32, 21000 Split, Croatia
Email: Marko.Vukasovic@fesb.hr, web page: <http://www.fesb.hr>

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ABSTRACT

An approximate shear deformable engineering theory of bending of thin-walled composite beams with open mono-symmetrical cross-sections is presented. It is assumed that the normal stresses in the transverse direction are small compared to the normal stresses in the longitudinal direction so that can be ignored in stress-strain relations. It is proved that the beam is subjected to bending with the influence of shear caused by forces in the plane of symmetry and in addition to tension/compression due to shear. The solution for the stresses and displacement are given in closed analytic form. Thin-walled cross-sections assembled of symmetric cross-ply and orthotropic unidirectional laminates are considered. The results are compared to the finite element method by several examples.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thin-walled composite beams with an open cross-section have been increasingly used over the past few decades as primary and secondary bearing structure elements, subjected to complex static and dynamic loading systems [1], [2]. For the static analysis of thin-walled composite beams subjected to bending, considerable research efforts have been made to obtain analytical solutions [3], [4], [5], [6]. Also, in order to evaluate deformation responses under these types of loading, finite element method has been widely used and large amount of work was devoted to the improvement of composite finite elements [7], [8].

It is well known that shear deformations have a significant influence on statics of thin-walled composite beams, due to the low values of shear modulus. Classic Euler-Bernoulli's beam theory, as well the Vlasov's thin-walled beam theory [9], [10], do not take into account shear deformation, making them improper in stress and displacement analyses of laminated thin-walled composite beams. It is possible to generalize Vlasov's theory by taking into account the shear deformation in beam midplane, so that relatively short thin-walled composite beams with open cross-section can be considered [5], [6], [11].

In this paper an approximate analytic solution for the stresses and displacements according to the theory of bending with the influence of shear [5], [6], [12], [13] is given for mono-symmetric thin-walled composite beams. The external load is reduced to the uniformly distributed forces per unit length, acting in the beam plane of symmetry. In that case beam is subjected to bending with the influence of shear and in addition to tension/compression due to shear. The shear factors with respect to bending and with respect to tension/compression are given in analytic forms as pure geometrical properties. Thin-walled cross-sections assembled of symmetric cross-ply and orthotropic unidirectional laminates are considered. For the purpose of analysis, the expressions for the factors of influence of shear on displacements and normal stresses are derived. The results obtained for simply supported and clamped beams with different length to height ratios are compared to results of the finite element analysis.

2 STRAINS AND DISPLACEMENTS

The displacement of an arbitrary point $S(x, s)$ at the middle line in the case of bending of thin-walled beams of open sections with respect to the xz -axis of symmetry can be expressed as (Figure 1):

$$u_s = -\frac{dw}{dx}z + u + \int_0^s \gamma_{x\xi} ds = \beta z + u + \int_0^s \gamma_{x\xi} ds, \quad \beta = -dw/dx, \quad (1)$$

where $w = w(x)$ is the displacement in the z -direction, i.e. the displacement of the cross-section middle line as a rigid line in the plane of symmetry, $z = z(s)$ is the rectangular coordinate, $u = u(x)$ is the displacement of the cross-section middle line as a rigid line in the x -direction, $\gamma_{x\xi} = \gamma_{x\xi}(x, s)$ is the shear strain in the beam middle surface, s is the curvilinear coordinate at the middle line, ξ is the tangential axis on the curvilinear coordinate s ; $Oxyz$ is the orthogonal coordinate system, where the z -axis is the axis of symmetry; $\beta = \beta(x)$ is the angular displacement of the middle line as a rigid line with respect to the y -axis, orthogonal to z -axis.

Figure 1: Portion of the cross-section middle line.

The displacements can be expressed as

$$w = w_b + w_a, \quad u = u_a, \quad (2)$$

where $w_b = w_b(x)$ is the displacement of the cross-sections as a plane sections in the z -direction, as in the case of the ordinary theory of bending, $w_a = w_a(x)$ is the additional displacement due to shear in the z -direction, $u_a = u_a(x)$ is the additional displacement due to shear in the x -direction. The angular displacements can be expressed as

$$\beta = \beta_b + \beta_a, \quad \beta_b = -dw_b/dx, \quad \beta_a = -dw_a/dx. \quad (3)$$

Thus, the strain in the longitudinal direction can be expressed as

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = -\frac{d^2w}{dx^2}z + \frac{du}{dx} + \int_0^s \frac{\partial \gamma_{x\xi}}{\partial x} ds. \quad (4)$$

3 STRESSES AND DISPLACEMENTS

The constitutive equation for in-plane stresses and strains in an arbitrary $x-\xi$ coordinate system may be written as follows [14]

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_\xi \\ \tau_{x\xi} \end{Bmatrix}^k = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & 0 \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix}^k \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_\xi \\ \gamma_{x\xi} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma_x^k = \sigma_x^k(x, s)$ is the normal stress in k -th ply in longitudinal x -direction; $\sigma_\xi^k = \sigma_\xi^k(x, s)$ is the normal stress in k -th ply in contour ξ -direction; $\tau_{x\xi}^k = \tau_{x\xi}^k(x, s)$ is the shear stress in k -th ply; \bar{Q}_{ij} are

transformed reduced stiffnesses and are consisted of material properties with respect to each ply. Constitutive equation can be simplified by using free stress in contour direction ($\sigma_\xi = 0$) assumption as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \tau_{x\xi} \end{Bmatrix}^k = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11}^* & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{Q}_{66}^* \end{bmatrix}^k \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \gamma_{x\xi} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where for free stress assumption

$$\bar{Q}_{11}^* = \bar{Q}_{11} - \frac{\bar{Q}_{12}^2}{\bar{Q}_{22}}, \quad \bar{Q}_{66}^* = \bar{Q}_{66}. \quad (7)$$

According to equations (4) and (6), normal stress in k -th ply in x -direction can be expressed as

$$\sigma_x^k = \bar{Q}_{11}^* \left(-\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} z + \frac{du}{dx} + \int_0^s \frac{\partial \gamma_{x\xi}}{\partial x} ds \right). \quad (8)$$

From the equilibrium of a differential portion of the k -th ply, it may be written

$$\tau_{x\xi}^k = \frac{1}{t^k} \left[-\int_0^s \frac{\partial (\sigma_x^k t^k)}{\partial x} ds + f^k(x) \right]; \quad f^k(x) = t^k (M) \cdot \tau_{x\xi}^k(x, M) = T_M^k(x), \quad (9)$$

where $t^k = t^k(s)$ is the constant ply thickness and M is the starting point of the curvilinear coordinate s . If $\partial \gamma_{x\xi} / \partial x = const.$, referring to (8), one has

$$\tau_{x\xi}^k = \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^*}{t} \left(\frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} S_y(s) - \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} A(s) \right) + \frac{T_M^k}{t^k}, \quad S_y(s) = \int_0^s z dA, \quad A(s) = \int_0^s dA, \quad dA = t ds, \quad (10)$$

$$\tau_{x\xi}^k = -\frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^*}{t} \left(\frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} S_y^* - \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} A^* \right), \quad S_y^* = \int_{s^*} z dA^*; \quad A^* = \int_{s^*} dA^*; \quad dA^* = t ds^*, \quad ds^* = -ds, \quad (11)$$

where $t = t(s)$ is the constant laminate thickness, $S_y^* = S_y^*(s)$ is the moment of the cut-off portion of area with respect to y -axis, $A^* = A^*(s)$ is the cut-off portion of area, s^* is the curvilinear coordinate of the cut-off portion of the beam wall area, from the edge, i.e. where $\tau_{x\xi}^k = 0$.

According to equation (6), shear strain in the beam middle surface may be written as

$$\gamma_{x\xi} = \frac{\tau_{x\xi}^k}{\bar{Q}_{66}^*}. \quad (12)$$

The expression for the shear strain (12) can be approximately rewritten under the assumption that the shear strain is constant along the laminate thickness

$$\gamma_{x\xi} \approx \frac{1}{t} \int_t \gamma_{x\xi} d\delta = k^\alpha \left(-\frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} \frac{S_y^*}{t} + \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} \frac{A^*}{t} \right), \quad (13)$$

where k^α is the factor of material influence on shear. Factor k^α is defined in above expression as follows

$$\int_t \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^*}{\bar{Q}_{66}^*} d\delta = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{\delta_{k-1}}^{\delta_k} \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^*}{\bar{Q}_{66}^*} d\delta = t \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^*}{\bar{Q}_{66}^*} \frac{t^k}{t} = k^\alpha t, \quad (14)$$

where N is the total number of plies in each laminate; δ^k and δ^{k-1} are coordinates of k -th ply with

respect to beam middle-surface. According to equations (8) and (13), normal stress σ_x^k in k -th ply can now be expressed as

$$\sigma_x^k = \bar{Q}_{11}^* \left(-\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} z + \frac{du}{dx} \right) + \bar{Q}_{11}^* k^\alpha \left(-\frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} \int_0^s \frac{S_y^*}{t} ds + \frac{d^3 u}{dx^3} \int_0^s \frac{A^*}{t} ds \right). \quad (15)$$

The average shear and normal stress in cross-section is obtained by integrating equations (11) and (15) along the wall thickness of the laminate

$$\tau_{x\xi,m} = \frac{1}{t} \int_t \tau_{x\xi}^k d\delta = -k^\beta \left(\frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} \frac{S_y^*}{t} - \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} \frac{A^*}{t} \right), \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_{x,m} = \frac{1}{t} \int_t \sigma_x^k d\delta = k^\beta \left(-\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} z + \frac{du}{dx} \right) + k^\beta k^\alpha \left(-\frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} \int_0^s \frac{S_y^*}{t} ds + \frac{d^3 u}{dx^3} \int_0^s \frac{A^*}{t} ds \right), \quad (17)$$

where k^β is the rigidity of laminates, defined in above expressions as

$$\int_t \bar{Q}_{11}^* d\delta = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{\delta_{k-1}}^{\delta_k} \bar{Q}_{11}^* d\delta = t \sum_{k=1}^N \bar{Q}_{11}^* \frac{t^k}{t} = k^\beta t. \quad (18)$$

4. EQUILIBRIUM EQUATIONS

For a portion of the beam wall, the following equilibrium equations can be written

$$\sum F_x = \iint_{L,t} \frac{\partial \sigma_x^k}{\partial x} dx d\delta ds = 0, \quad \sum F_z = \iint_{L,t} \frac{\partial \tau_{x\xi}^k}{\partial x} \sin \varphi dx d\delta ds + q_z dx = 0, \quad (19)$$

$$\iint_{L,t} \frac{\partial \tau_{x\xi}^k}{\partial x} d\delta dz + q_z = 0, \quad \sin \varphi = \frac{dz}{ds}, \quad (20)$$

where $q_z = q_z(x)$ are the forces per unit length acting in the beam plane of symmetry.

Referring to equations (8) and (10) one has

$$-k^\beta S_y \frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} + k^\beta A \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} = 0, \quad k^\beta I_y \frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} - k^\beta S_y \frac{d^3 u}{dx^3} = q_z, \quad A = \int_A dA, \quad I_y = \int_A z^2 dA, \quad (21)$$

where due to symmetry $S_y = \int_A z dA = 0$. Thus

$$\frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} = 0, \quad k^\beta I_y \frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} = q_z. \quad (22)$$

5. INTERNAL FORCES AND STRESSES

Integration of the shear stress components $\tau_{x\xi}^k$ over the cross-sections gives

$$\iint_{L,t} \tau_{x\xi}^k \sin \varphi d\delta ds = Q_z, \quad (23)$$

where $Q_z = Q_z(x)$ is the shear force with respect to z -axis. Substitution of equation (11) into equation (23) gives

$$Q_z = -k^\beta I_y \frac{d^3 w}{dx^3}, \quad \int_L S_y^* dz = \int_A z^2 dA = I_y. \quad (24)$$

Referring to equations (22) gives

$$dQ_z/dx = -q_z. \quad (25)$$

Thus, by substituting equations (22) and (24) into equations (11) and (16)

$$\tau_{x\xi}^k = Q_z \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^* S_y^*}{k^\beta t I_y}, \quad \tau_{x\xi,m} = \frac{Q_z S_y^*}{I_y t}. \quad (26)$$

Integration of the normal stress components σ_x^k over the cross-section gives

$$\int_L \int_t \sigma_x^k d\delta ds = 0, \quad M_y = \int_L \int_t \sigma_x^k z d\delta ds, \quad (27)$$

where $M_y = M_y(x)$ is the bending moment with respect to y-axis. By substituting equation (15) into equations (27), the following expression can be obtained

$$k^\beta A \frac{du}{dx} - N^z = 0, \quad M_y = -k^\beta I_y \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} - M_y^z, \quad (28)$$

where

$$N^z = \frac{q_z k^\alpha}{I_y} \int_A dA \int_0^s \frac{S_y^*}{t} ds = \frac{q_z k^\alpha}{I_y} \int_L \frac{A^* S_y^*}{t} ds, \quad (29)$$

$$M_y^z = \frac{q_z k^\alpha}{I_y} \int_A z dA \int_0^s \frac{S_y^*}{t} ds = \frac{q_z k^\alpha}{I_y} \int_A \left(\frac{S_y^*}{t} \right)^2 dA. \quad (30)$$

Referring to equations (22), (24) and (28), the following expressions can be written

$$\frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} = \frac{dN^z}{dx} = 0, \quad -k^\beta I_y \frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} = \frac{dM_y}{dx} + \frac{dM_y^z}{dx} = Q_z, \quad -k^\beta I_y \frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} = \frac{d^2 M_y}{dx^2} = \frac{dQ_z}{dx} = -q_z. \quad (31)$$

The normal stress given by equations (15) and (17), referring to equations (22) and (28), can be expressed as

$$\sigma_x^k = M_y \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^*}{k^\beta I_y} z + M_y^z \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^*}{k^\beta I_y} z + N^z \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^*}{k^\beta A} - q_z \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^* k^\alpha}{k^\beta I_y} \int_0^s \frac{S_y^*}{t} ds, \quad (32)$$

$$\sigma_{x,m} = \frac{M_y}{I_y} z + \frac{M_y^z}{I_y} z + \frac{N^z}{A} - q_z \frac{k^\alpha}{I_y} \int_0^s \frac{S_y^*}{t} ds. \quad (33)$$

The components given by equations (29) and (30) can also be written as

$$N^z = q_z k^\alpha \kappa_{xz} L_S, \quad \kappa_{xz} = \frac{1}{I_y L_S} \int_A \frac{A^* S_y^*}{t^2} dA, \quad (34)$$

$$M_y^z = q_z \frac{k^\alpha \kappa_{zz} I_y}{A}, \quad \kappa_{zz} = \frac{A}{I_y^2} \int_A \left(\frac{S_y^*}{t} \right)^2 dA, \quad (35)$$

where κ_{zz} and κ_{xz} are the shear factors with respect to w -displacements and to the u -displacements (due to the w -displacements), respectively; L_S is an arbitrary length of the middle line.

Hence, the normal stress given by equations (32) and (33) can also be written as

$$\sigma_x^k = M_y \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^*}{k^\beta I_y} z + q_z \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^* k^\alpha \kappa_{zz}}{k^\beta A} z + q_z \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^* k^\alpha \kappa_{xz} L_S}{k^\beta A} - q_z \frac{\bar{Q}_{11}^* k^\alpha}{k^\beta I_y} \int_0^s \frac{S_y^*}{t} ds, \quad (36)$$

$$\sigma_{x,m} = \frac{M_y}{I_y} z + q_z \frac{k^\alpha \kappa_{zz}}{A} z + q_z \frac{k^\alpha \kappa_{xz} L_S}{A} - q_z \frac{k^\alpha}{I_y} \int_0^s \frac{S_y^*}{t} ds. \quad (37)$$

6 DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS WITH SEPARATED DISPLACEMENTS

Equations (28), according to equations (34) and (35), can be expressed as

$$\frac{du}{dx} = \frac{q_z k^\alpha L_S \kappa_{xz}}{k^\beta A}, \quad \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} = -\frac{M_y}{k^\beta I_y} - \frac{q_z k^\alpha \kappa_{zz}}{k^\beta A}. \quad (38)$$

According to equation (2), the above expressions can be separated as

$$\frac{du}{dx} = \frac{du_a}{dx} = \frac{q_z k^\alpha L_S \kappa_{xz}}{k^\beta A}, \quad \frac{d^2 w_b}{dx^2} = -\frac{M_y}{k^\beta I_y}, \quad \frac{d^2 w_a}{dx^2} = -\frac{q_z k^\alpha \kappa_{zz}}{k^\beta A}. \quad (39)$$

Integrating and taking into account equations (3) and (25), the following expressions are obtained

$$u_a = -Q_z \frac{k^\alpha L_S \kappa_{xz}}{k^\beta A}, \quad \frac{dw_a}{dx} = -\beta_a = Q_z \frac{k^\alpha \kappa_{zz}}{k^\beta A}. \quad (40)$$

Integration constants are ignored in above equations. It is assumed that the additional longitudinal displacement u_a , as well as the angular displacement β_a , do not depend on the boundary conditions. Second expression in the equation (39) is analogue to the well known equation of the classical theory of bending of thin-walled beams, where

$$k^\beta I_y \frac{d^3 w_b}{dx^3} = -\frac{dM_y}{dx} = -Q_z, \quad k^\beta I_y \frac{d^4 w_b}{dx^4} = -\frac{d^2 M_y}{dx^2} = -\frac{dQ_z}{dx} = q_z, \quad \frac{dw_b}{dx} = -\beta_b. \quad (41)$$

Integrating second expression of equation (40) it is obtained that

$$w_a = \frac{k^\alpha \kappa_{zz}}{k^\beta A} M_y + C_w, \quad (42)$$

where C_w is the integration constant with respect to the w -displacements.

7 BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

According to equation (42), boundary conditions at the starting section A can be defined as

$$w_a = 0, \quad C_w = -M_{yA} \frac{k^\alpha \kappa_{zz}}{k^\beta A}, \quad (43)$$

where M_{yA} is the bending moment at $x = x_A$. The total displacements then are

$$w = w_b + (M_y - M_{yA}) \frac{k^\alpha \kappa_{zz}}{k^\beta A}, \quad u_a = -Q_z \frac{k^\alpha L_S \kappa_{xz}}{k^\beta A}. \quad (44)$$

For simply supported beams, for hinged sections A and B, it may be written

$$w|_{x=x_{A,B}} = w_b|_{x=x_{A,B}} = 0, \quad \left. \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right|_{x=x_{A,B}} = \left. \frac{d^2 w_b}{dx^2} \right|_{x=x_{A,B}} = 0 \quad (M_{yA,B} = 0). \quad (45)$$

For the clamped sections it may be written

$$w|_{x=x_A} = w_b|_{x=x_A} = 0 \quad \frac{dw_b}{dx}|_{x=x_A} = 0 \quad (\beta_A^b = 0),$$

$$w|_{x=x_B} = w_b|_{x=x_B} + \frac{k^\alpha \kappa_{zz}}{k^\beta A} \left(-k^\beta I_y \frac{d^2 w_b}{dx^2} \Big|_{x=x_B} + k^\beta I_y \frac{d^2 w_b}{dx^2} \Big|_{x=x_A} \right) = 0, \quad \frac{dw_b}{dx} \Big|_{x=x_B} = 0 \quad (\beta_B^b = 0). \quad (46)$$

8 SHEAR FACTORS

The normal stress at the junction of the web and the bottom flange (Figure 2), according to equation (37), can be expressed as

$$\sigma_{x,m} = \lambda \frac{M_y}{I_y} \cdot h_T^C, \quad (47)$$

where for beams loaded by uniformly distributed forces per unit length, for the beam midspan, the following factors of influence of shear on normal stress are given

$$\lambda = 1 + 8 \frac{k^\alpha I_y \kappa_{zz}}{Al^2} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\kappa_{xz}}{\kappa_{zz}} \cdot \frac{h}{h_T^C} - \frac{A(3A_2 + t_0 h_T^C) h_T^C}{3t_0 I_y \kappa_{zz}} \right), \quad (48)$$

$$\lambda = 1 + 24 \frac{k^\alpha I_y \kappa_{zz}}{Al^2} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\kappa_{xz}}{\kappa_{zz}} \cdot \frac{h}{h_T^C} - \frac{A(3A_2 + t_0 h_T^C) h_T^C}{3t_0 I_y \kappa_{zz}} \right), \quad (49)$$

for simply supported and clamped beams, respectively.

Figure 2: Simple mono-symmetrical cross-section

The total displacement, according to equation (44), can be expressed as

$$w = \eta w_b, \quad (50)$$

where for beams loaded by uniformly distributed forces per unit length, for the beam midspan, the following factors of influence shear on vertical displacements are given

$$\eta = 1 + \frac{48 k^\alpha \kappa_{zz} I_y}{5 Al^2}, \quad (51)$$

$$\eta = 1 + 48 \frac{k^\alpha \kappa_{zz} I_y}{Al^2}, \quad (52)$$

for simply supported beams and clamped beams. For simple mono-symmetrical cross-section, according to equations (34) and (35), shear factors are defined as

$$\kappa_{zz} = \frac{\varphi^2 (1 + \chi + \psi)^3 \left[\frac{\varphi}{\psi} (1 + \chi^2 \mu^3) + \frac{2}{3} \varphi^2 (1 + \chi \mu^4) + \frac{2}{15} \psi \varphi^3 (1 + \mu^5) + \frac{1}{12} \rho^2 (1 + \chi \mu^2 \zeta^2) \right]}{\left[\chi + \frac{1}{3} \psi \left(1 + \chi + \frac{1}{4} \psi \right) \right]^2}, \quad (53)$$

$$\kappa_{xz} = - \frac{\varphi (1 + \chi + \psi) \left[24 \varphi (1 - \chi^2 \mu^2) + 2 \psi \rho^2 (1 - \chi \mu \zeta^2) + 20 \psi \varphi^2 (1 - \chi \mu^3) + 5 \psi^2 \varphi^3 (1 - \mu^4) \right]}{2 \psi \left[12 \chi + \psi (4 + \psi + 4 \chi) \right]}, \quad (54)$$

where $\chi = A_2 / A_1$, $\psi = A_0 / A_1$, $\zeta = b_2 / b_1$, $\rho = b_1 / h$, $\mu = h_t^C / h_t^B$, $\varphi = h_t^B / h$, $A = A_1 (1 + \chi + \psi)$.

9 ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

Developed analytical model is limited to the analysis of thin-walled composite beams assembled of symmetrical laminates with constant rigidity along the cross-section contour line. For that reason, orthotropic unidirectional and cross-ply laminates were taken into account. The cross-section properties are defined according to Figure 2: $b_1 = 40$ mm, $b_2 = 30$ mm, $h = 50$ mm, $t_1 = 3.12$ mm, $t_0 = 1.04$ mm, $t_2 = 2.08$ mm. The detailed stacking sequences of mono-symmetrical I-beam, for orthotropic unidirectional (ANG0) and symmetric cross-ply (ANG0/90) laminate configuration, are summarized in Table 1.

Configuration	Top flange	Bottom flange	Web
ANG0	[0] ₂₄	[0] ₁₆	[0] ₈
ANG0/90	[0/90] _{6s}	[0/90] _{4s}	[0/90] _{2s}

Table 1: Stacking sequence of mono-symmetrical I-beam

The distributed line load of $q_z = 1$ N/mm is applied at neutral axis of the cross-section. The material models are analysed with following properties for composite material: $E_1 = 53.78$ GPa, $E_2 = E_3 = 17.93$ GPa, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 8.96$ GPa, $G_{23} = 3.45$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.25$, $\nu_{23} = 0.34$ [5].

The factors λ and η , obtained analytically using equations (48), (49), (51) and (52), for simply supported and clamped beams are compared with numerically obtained results by applying the finite element method using ADINA software [15]. The 9-noded shell elements are used for the FEM analysis of 3D geometry model. In that case only one half of the model is analysed using corresponding boundary conditions at the beam midspan and at the starting sections (simple supported and clamped boundary conditions). The analyses are performed for two different beam aspect ratios ($l/h = 3$ and $l/h = 5$). The results at the beam midspan are given in Table 2 and Table 3.

l/h	ANG0				ANG0/90			
	Simply supported (48)		Clamped (49)		Simply supported (48)		Clamped (49)	
	FEM	FEM	FEM	FEM	FEM	FEM	FEM	FEM
3	1.178	1.175	1.536	1.483	1.119	1.104	1.357	1.299
5	1.064	1.066	1.192	1.183	1.042	1.036	1.128	1.108

Table 2: The factors λ , according to (48) and (49), for ANG0 and ANG0/90 stacking sequence

l/h	ANG0				ANG0/90			
	Simply supported (51)		Clamped (52)		Simply supported (51)		Clamped (52)	
	FEM	FEM	FEM	FEM	FEM	FEM	FEM	FEM
3	7.039	7.256	31.196	31.943	5.026	5.085	21.132	21.273
5	3.174	3.206	11.870	11.939	2.449	2.453	8.274	8.244

Table 3: The factors η , according to (51) and (52), for ANG0 and ANG0/90 stacking sequence

10 CONCLUSION

An approximate analytical solution for bending of thin-walled composite beams with mono-symmetrical cross-sections is given. It is proved that the beam with one axis of symmetry, loaded by transverse load in the plane of symmetry, is subjected to bending with influence of shear and to tension/compression due to shear. As an example, thin-walled beams made of symmetrical, orthotropic unidirectional and cross-ply laminates are taken into account. The shear factors are presented in the parametric form, in order to evaluate the influence of shear for different beam lengths, different boundary conditions as well as for different stacking sequences of laminates. It is shown that the shear influence is significant for displacements with respect to the ones obtained by the classical theories, and must be taken into account even in the case of higher beam aspect ratios. On the other hand, the influence of shear on normal stresses is less expressed and can be neglected for relatively long beams. Several examples are analyzed according to the presented theory and they are compared with the solutions obtained by the finite element method. Excellent agreements of the results are obtained for the displacements, as well as for stresses.

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